

EVOLUTION OF FINGERPRINT AND FINGER VEIN BIOMETRICS

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ABSTRACT

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INTRODUCTION

Biometric systems address numerous requirements, including broad population coverage, demographic diversity, a variety of deployment environments, as well as practical concerns like performance and spoofing threats. Traditional unimodal biometric systems fall short of the standards, leaving them open to many forms of intrusions and rendering them insecure. To get beyond unimodal biometric systems' limitations and achieve high recognition accuracy, multimodal biometric systems have been deployed extensively. Most multimodal systems, however, need several steps to collect multimodal biometric data, and this necessitates certain user behaviours, which causes users to feel inconvenienced. For strong and trustworthy identity verification, multimodal biometric systems based on finger vein and fingerprint modality provide promising qualities [1].

ADVANTAGES OF FINGERPRINT AND FINGER VEIN MULTIMODAL SYSTEM OVER OTHER MULTIMODALS.

Among the different biometric modalities that can be used to constitute a multimodal biometric system the use of fingerprint and finger vein appears to be more refined because

1. The human fingers are highly convenient for imaging and disclose variety of features when captured in different spectrums. For instance, imaging the finger with visible spectrum will disclose the texture features present on the finger surface that in turn can be used to extract minutiae features of the fingerprint or the line features of the whole finger. While imaging the finger with a near infrared spectrum will allow one to capture the finger vein pattern.
2. Low verification error rates can be achieved by combining these complementary features available from the single biometric modality i.e, finger
3. Use of finger-vein shows strong anti-spoofing nature as it is hidden inside the finger and cannot be stolen without subject co-operation.
4. The two biometric characteristics can be acquired with one capture device and in principle with a single capture attempt. These factors motivate us to explore a new capture device to reliably observe the prominent information from the finger that in turn can be used to build a multimodal biometric system using fingerprint and finger vein images for robust identity verification.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

- [1] R. Raghavendra, K. B. Raja, J. Surbiryala, and C. Busch, "A low-cost multimodal biometric sensor to capture finger vein and fingerprint," in *IEEE International joint conference on biometrics*, 2014: IEEE, pp. 1-7.